

Who are you?

Designing interpretations for new interpretations

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Abstract: User-centred design is a widely acknowledged practice. Much attention has been put into methods, tools, and processes on how to collect information, insights and stories from users. Currently, more and more effort is invested into engaging various stakeholders in collaborative design efforts and nurturing an attitude of human centeredness as a strategy. This attitude addresses design empathy, which is the ability to step into another person's shoes and looking at the world from that perspective. The objective of this paper is to illustrate and discuss different kind of formats that can be used to communicate representations of user study/field findings and insights in a way that can be open ended for new interpretations and allow and inspire personal insights. The paper describes several examples in which the issue has been addressed.

Key words: *user centred design, co-design, communication, design empathy, user representations*

1. Introduction

Empathic design approaches can start thinking processes within individuals in which they try to relate their own experiences in order to understand other people and their experiences [1]. The participants of such activities - users, designers and other stakeholders, are thus invited to get personally, emotionally engaged, reflecting on who they are and who are the people they are designing for and with. Reading (thick) user study reports from the field, as often stated, is not the best way to support empathic attitudes or creative processes in design projects and alike. But what are the alternatives? Questions such as what to communicate, to whom and when, as well how to do so are not commonplace.

One of the main concerns in user-centred design is that various domains of knowledge are collaborating (e.g. users, designer, other professional stakeholders). Distinct professional domains often have their own ways of communicating and documenting based on conventions that are understandable within the domain but usually foreign for others. Another concern is that there are differences between communicating end results, and presenting preliminary results as part of an ongoing process. The objective of this paper is to illustrate and discuss different kind of formats that can be used to communicate representations of user study/field findings and insights in a way that can be open ended for new interpretations and allow and inspire personal insights. The paper describes several examples in which these concerns have been consciously addressed.

2. Incompleteness

Field study ‘documents’ are always incomplete. They can never cover everything but will always create an incomplete picture of the world they try to describe. When anthropologists conduct field studies, they usually spend several months and even years in the field in order to understand the chosen culture. The famous anthropologist Clifford Geertz writes that culture, is "a system of inherited conceptions expressed in symbolic forms by means of which people communicate, perpetuate, and develop their knowledge about and attitudes toward life" [2, p. 89]. Geertz suggests the notion of thick descriptions as describing the results of the ethnographers work; the ethnography. He argues that a thick description of human behaviour should describe not only the behaviour but also the context as well, so that the behaviour becomes meaningful to an outsider. This result is very different from that of designers’ field study results, which aims mainly at providing inspiration and information for suggesting ‘other futures’ through designing a material or immaterial products and services.

Based on differing needs in design projects the time spent in the field studies is much shorter than in traditional ethnographic field studies. For the same reason we often talk about applying ethnographic inspired field methods like observations and interviews. The results of these studies differ from traditional ethnographic studies. It has become more wide spread to supplement the ethnographic inspired field methods with applying various experimental approaches in user studies. The outcomes of such approaches can be fragmented and even surprising [see e.g. 3]. One of the ways to benefit of the fragmented characteristics and to create a more coherent picture about people and their experiences is apply storytelling for sharing and creating insights. Storytelling can be said to include two separate stories, one is the story being told by someone. The other story is the listeners’ story, which they create in their minds based on their experience and interpretation of the story being told. [4]

As an example of experimental field study methods mentioned above is the (design) probes approach [3, 5]. The probes are based on self-documenting: the users are given probes kits including tasks such as diaries and open questions, for communicating and reflecting their experiences. Already the designing of the probing kits is a beginning of a communication process. The designers initiate the dialogue through the questions and materials provided. It is followed up by the 'users' filling out the probing kits with their personal experiences and interpretations of 'what the designers are after'. The designers interpret the 'answers', invite the ‘users’ for an interview about their probes for getting more insight about their thoughts, and the stories connected to the potential design ideas.

Probes approach is a tool for collecting user data, but also a tool and a process for collaborative exploration [6]. One of the reasons for using probes is involving organizations and stakeholders into discussion to co-explore, share interpretations and to create new understandings, e.g. in workshops early in the design process [5]. The objective of probing then is about orienting towards users’ context and getting an understanding of the subjective elements of the context such as emotions, lifestyle, motivations and values. Typically the team organizes collaborative sessions for creating and sharing interpretations. The outcomes of such studies and sessions are various kinds of user representations that can be utilized as inspiration and to raise the awareness of user perspective. More intangible outcomes are about design empathy and collaborative learning among the participants.

A valuable example of how the challenge of communicating exploratory field data has been addressed is Sleeswijk Visser's [7] study. She explored how results of fuzzy front end user studies can be communicated to industrial (product design) practice in a useful way. Based on her findings she stresses three guidelines for the communication: inspiration, empathy and engagement. Based on these guidelines the findings from the user study material is communicated by selecting extracts from the original material, such as quotes, and making open ended suggestions for the interpretations through pointing some key issues and their relations. The deliverables do not then produce a shortcut to a final result, but rather a map showing possible directions or paths, risks and opportunities to support the designer's interpretation and orientation. This way of working requires designers' ability to look ahead, suggesting possible paths meaningful to design. Thus, designing becomes then as a crucial part of the interpretation process, first when making decisions about what seems to be meaningful for design but also as the field data needs to be communicated in a way that supports empathy, inspiration and engagement. Sleeswijk Visser's studies addressed product design context. However, more and more of user studies and co-design related projects are conducted outside the traditional design field and are not related to specific categories of product design. Then the task of identifying possible paths to communicate becomes even more challenging.

An alternative approach of working with user data was presented by Nugent et al [8]. Art Center College of Design's students conducted a study, also using probes methods among others, on LA families' nature relationships. The interpretation was mainly conducted through making designerly artefacts, thus the original data was transformed into and treated as design material. They used a variety of media from visual collages, personas, video, personal notes and even 3 dimensional representations were exhibited in what they called an 'Open-Ended Knowledge Environment'. The exhibition itself was a visual interpretation of the study as such. It aimed at "allowing ambiguous interpreting, learning, empathizing, and creating new input with insights and storytelling." [ibid p. 278] This case inspires to think if similar kind of artistic exercises could be conducted also elsewhere, beyond student projects.

In user driven innovation it is essential to getting to know "the other", the people and contexts to design for. In this sense one can say that when designers enter the world of (potential) users it is based on similar aims as ethnographers entering the field; getting familiar with the environment, peoples' behaviours, beliefs, aspirations etc. As mentioned by Halse et al.[9] familiarization in design "is bringing to light the myriad of unexpected (sometimes innovative) ways that people put products and services to use in their everyday lives" [5, p. 65]. It is through field studies and interpretation of field data that designers and other stakeholders learn about (potential) 'users and contexts of use'. However, what seems even more powerful as both a learning and innovation potential is deconstructing the familiar in order to estrange the familiar. It is through estrangement that existing knowledge is "cast in new light" [ibid, p. 65]. Constantly striving for engaging various stakeholders in processes of familiarization and estrangement combined with co-creation approaches for 'rehearsing possible futures' addresses incompleteness and partiality as a positive and productive norm in user driven innovation [ibid, p. 36]. It requires open-ended communication and design representations. In the following we will describe several case studies conducted by the authors in research projects in collaboration with university researchers and companies. In these cases the communication of user study insights were purposefully left open ended. The examples represent cases in which user-centred design approach can be useful beyond product design. The first one opens

a hospital environment from nurse's point of view. The second case deals with a social challenge. The third case opens up a service context in which several companies need to network to collaborate and the fourth case touches upon innovation efforts in the complex world of waste handling.

3. Open ended stories

3.1. Posters to challenge viewers' perceptions of nurses and their practice

The first case example is a study of nurses and patient transportation [5, 10]. This study was conducted as part of a research project in collaboration with a design consultancy and a global corporation that operates in the field of patient monitoring. The researchers' objective in the study was experimenting with empathic probes in work context while the companies' interest was in learning new ways of gaining user understanding. The study aimed at assisting people within the companies to face personal image of nurses and their situations at work and reflect upon their insights. With the probes and interviews that followed a holistic but fragmented understanding of the work community, instruments and situations from the individual nurse's point of view was created.

Figure 1. On the left one of the three posters representing the nurses, sized 1m x1m. The circle as a graphical element aimed to raise people's interest. On the right, a detail from the poster: a collage explaining patient transportation situations.

A crucial part of the case was reporting the outcomes of the empathic material. There was no interest in applying traditional formats like written reports. Instead we wanted to tell stories and inspire discussions and new interpretations. Thus, in addition to a digital presentation that highlighted the key findings of the study, the material from probes, such as photos and quotes were selected and designed into three posters that were placed in the product development area in the companies. These posters were representations of three 'real' nurses, with their own words, pictures taken by them, as well as with the probe material, such as cards and diary pages completed by them.

The idea behind these posters was to break stereotypical views of nurses and their working environment and bringing the users into the working context as reminders of whom the developers are designing for. The posters showed a broad and personal image of the hospital world rather than focusing on the use of products. The posters worked as hoped for: people started asking questions about them, such as where they came from and questioning the truthfulness of specific details. The posters thus created discussions and people started to share their experiences and comparing them with the ones presented on the posters. Based on the feedback this individual perspective detached from the company's products as well as the visual and explorative nature of the probing approach, were regarded as refreshing in a company where user-centred activities are part of the daily practice.

3.2. Persona booklets to tell stories about ageing workers' individual characteristics

The second case is from the Active@work project that dealt with the challenge of the ageing population [11]. The main objective was to identify possibilities that would support individual workers' sustainable well-being and motivation and avoid early retirement. The ageing individuals that were engaged in the study worked in school environments in cleaning and technical maintenance. In the project we had several stakeholders to consider as the audience of the findings included the management of the collaborative organization and international partners in two other EU countries.

Figure 2. On the left and in the middle: pages from the persona booklets representing the ageing worker characters and their work. On the right, booklets are reflected upon during a workshop.

The project had an open focus to start with and it was approached with a combination of different methods such as focus groups, observations, probes, and participatory workshops. In an iterative process the direction of the study as well as the alternative design solutions were reflected upon throughout the process. The probes approach was applied in the early phase of the project in order to broadly map the everyday working life, motivations and problems of the individual workers, and to sensitize them to reflect and report their experiences and concerns during the following phases of the project.

In the overall project we aimed at several outcomes. First, we needed to identify problems and potentials concerning the challenge of ageing at work, and report them to the stakeholders. Second, we developed and illustrated alternative concepts as solutions to tackle the challenge. Third, we wanted especially to understand and value individual people and their experiences, and use that understanding in the design process as well as to share our findings with the project's stakeholders. In the interpretation of the probing material we had identified eight particular persona characteristics and selected to use them as a way to communicate the individual perspective. The characters were named accordingly, e.g. Harry Helper, Eric Expert, Irene Inspirer. The descriptions summarized each persona's attitudes towards work, technology and teamwork, and their tasks. Their typical workdays were also composed into a story. All the descriptions were collected into A4 sized booklets. The objectives of these booklets and the characters were to draw attention to the ageing people, support the creation of a common understanding of their needs and motivations and to engage designers and other stakeholders in implementing this understanding in their decisions.

The booklets served as a knowledge base for the project in many ways. For instance they were the key tool in workshops, meetings and seminars to support the empathic discussion and decision making to initiate development activities from the individual worker's perspective. Already when the booklet drafts were

introduced to the ageing workers for feedback we noticed that the possibility to hear fellow workers' thoughts and combining daily working routines stimulated comments about e.g. individual attitudes and team spirit.

The booklets were delivered to various stakeholders as one of the results of the project. With their help, we wanted to continue supporting collaboration among the ageing workers, their superiors and other stakeholders in the process, such as health care and education providers. Narrative and visual booklets were easily adopted also beyond the project by people involved e.g. in occupational health and tacit knowledge in organizations. They provided a touch point to empathically understand the ageing workers' context and their well-being at work. In this case thus, the outcomes travelled much further than we had earlier planned for, which suggests that they were useful communication tool for new interpretations beyond the original scope.

3.3. Two approaches for communicating interviews from senior housing

The third case introduces two examples, Character Game and Senior expo, both from a Senior life case that was conducted in collaboration with KONE, a global corporation specialized in elevators and escalators. The researchers' focus was to explore novel ways of communicating field data on seniors and senior housing in an empathic and inspirational way keeping three main objectives in mind. Firstly, to utilize user data as source for new business networks; secondly, raising awareness of seniors as special user group; and thirdly, to promote company's shift in design towards more holistic understanding of 'people flow', a concept that is part of KONE's identity and can be widely understood as how people move in and around buildings. The first agenda included working with three companies connected with house manufacturing, whereas the second and third objectives mainly concerned company's particular R&D department.

Based on the project's overall aims the researchers developed a "Character Game" that was played in a co-design session and "Senior Expo" that was exhibited in the company's R&D department. The design game and the expo were both based on the user data gathered by the company's usability experts consisting of 28 interviews. The user study focused on senior houses and 'people flow'.

3.3.1 Stepping into seniors' shoes through role-playing

The basic principle of the Character Game was to let the participants to step outside their professional roles and put on senior's shoes to envision the world from that perspective. The researchers were inspired by the table-top role-playing games to combine quotations and images from the seniors and senior houses with players' own experiences through role-taking and storytelling. Evoking memories and attitudes through the game material and game playing were considered important in order to support the empathy building. The following explains briefly the steps of the game, while the approach is explained in detail in [12].

First, everyone told a personal story related to seniors. Second, printed images and quotes from the user study were placed on a paper to build a game world that illustrated the senior house. This aimed at visualizing the context and open the discussion related to senior housing. Third, the facilitator gave a brief description of the imagined senior house in which the (play) characters to be created in the following step would live in. Fourth, the participants were provided six different character templates from which everyone chose one as a base for his role character for the game. The role scripts [13, p 257-258] included specifications to support the role-playing,

mainly quotes from the interviews, which gave hints about personalities and disabilities. Things excluded from the templates were gender, careers, family ties and other personal information that were left to the participants to decide. To make the character creation more playful one random factor card were distributed to each player. It contained some secret background of the character that could be used in the game: "You have won the lottery" or "You have a bypass surgery scheduled in two months." Cards with images of elderly people were given to choose from as an image to represent the character. One picture was placed in front of each player on the table to work as a reminder. Fifth, the group chose one of the provided weekly schedules with a variety in service level to drive the activities taking place.

Figure 3. Character Game materials and players

Alike in tabletop role-playing games the unfolding of the Character Game was based on scenarios or scenes situated in the game world. Thus, as the sixth step the facilitator reads out first scene and after that each player gets to be a director in his turn. The director then introduces the scene, stemming from the weekly schedule. For example: "Ella and Aleksis are going to the pharmacy to get their medication. When they arrive at the elevator they notice it is broken. They try to figure out whom to notify." The scene ends when they decide to call for a janitor. Finally, after framing the scene, it is acted out by those whose role characters are in it. The metaphor of radio-play demonstrates the style of the performance in which the players sit around a table, and the story is acted out verbally without strong bodily engagement.

To reach information and inspiration, the game included general play-elements and contextualized content. For instance in the Character Game we introduced play-elements like role-taking, random factor cards, turn-taking and game world but grounded the activity to the themes found from the field data, such as monthly info meeting, in order to enable playing with purpose. By letting the players create their own character was important to make them consider the values, life situation, needs and desires which all should help directing the actions during the game. It seemed that by utilizing their own insights while building the role, the characters became detailed enough to feel 'real'. The character templates ensured that the link to the original user data was maintained even though participants' input and interpretations were essential for unfolding of the game.

When the participants generated stories that were partly based on their own past experiences, and partly prompted by the game material, i.e. user data, the co-created stories included several design openings; new scenarios and services were 'produced' as the story evolved. As expected, the game was found helpful in illustrating the whole service ecology, and consequently pointed out touch points where networked companies could collaborate. As for building empathy, the narrative nature and structured role-playing transform the players away from day to day roles. Even though the stories were placed in the game reality, the motifs and content were drawn from the user data but reflected players' own experiences, assumptions, and attitudes as well. Many participants mentioned afterwards that the Character Game opened up the world of the users, their values, needs,

and problems to them in a new way. The way the players described the overall feeling of the game session varied from being “relaxed”, “inspiring”, “eyes-opening” and “positive”. In the follow-up interviews the interviewed persons agreed on the usefulness of these types of approaches in the fuzzy-front-end of design processes, where problems are formulated. Instead of gaining new tools for participants’ current work practices, the game was seen as relevant to evoke discussions on seniors and the concept of ‘people flow’ in general.

3.3.2 Senior life expo to evoke emotional responses towards seniors

As part of experimenting with new ways of representing user data we wanted to try out a more artistic way and decided on designing an exhibition. This idea was inspired by Miya Zane Osaki’s Retellings exhibition that presented a collection of stories [14]. The Senior life exhibition was built on the same data as Character Game and was created around four key themes identified during two game sessions; me and others, aesthetic usability, moving, and feeling safety. These themes were introduced through four main characters that represented the people living in senior houses. The exhibition format aimed at letting the visitors to explore, feel and reflect. The purpose was to share some of the insights and questions that arose during the case study, not to present concept ideas. Thus, while exploring the exhibition everyone could create his own personal view on the topics.

Figure 4: The exhibition stated provocative and stereotypical notions, such as text “Who am I?” painted on the mirror to which people are asked to look at while wearing a mask of an older man.

One of the purposes of the exhibition was to promote company’s shift from mainly developing elevators and escalators to focusing on more broadly on people moving about. The four characters in the core of exhibition had distinct abilities and needs regarding to moving around, e.g. one needed a walking stick, whereas one didn’t have strengths in her arms. To concretize different attitudes and challenges they faced when moving, the expo included several touch points from an image of an elevator to a real garbage can connected to descriptive quotations such as “It would be nice if there were some softness in the lobby. There is an iron bench now. Plastic plant would also be nice.” “The elevator causes blood pressure. When going shopping you never know whether you get home. Or, when you have a laundry day. Since everybody else here is also aged, you can’t ask them for help. Once when the elevator was broken, I had to call my son to come from Järvenpää [30 km away] because I couldn’t go home with all the bags I had.”

With the design of the expo the researchers’ wanted to evoke emotions through raising questions such as: How do the things you see in the exhibition relate to you, your parents or grandparents? Derived from the artistic approach and the wish to show some of the seniors fears and dreams, the exhibition stated provocative and stereotypical notions, such as a wall with ‘old photos’ of the characters and quotations from the interviews

indicating seniors' distinct values, life styles and histories to promote their individuality. This was to underline that when people get older their needs and wishes become even more diverse than before.

As expected the expo evoked positive and negative opinions within R&D staff; some wanted to see more of this kind presentations of user studies, whereas some questioned whether it was worth the resources spent. The company representatives who were engaged in the case study considered the expo as a marketing tool for their business partners and clients; besides in-house learning there was visual evidence of company's innovativeness and willingness to better understand the end-users. Since the project is on-going we don't know what practical consequences the game and expo will have in the long term.

3.4. Inspiration in a box – User-driven innovation within the waste sector

The fourth case example is about working with the notion of 'all-in-a-box' as a re-thinking of deliverables for user-driven innovation. As part of a larger research project on developing a design anthropological innovation model a pilot project with a Danish incineration facility, Vestforbrænding was conducted. Vestforbrænding is a non-profit organization for waste handling owned by 19 municipalities in the greater Copenhagen area. The assignment was to challenge existing methods and approaches to waste handling through design-oriented dialogues where citizens, together with professional stakeholders, explore and unfold innovation potentials. The objective was to produce a workable innovation model and a toolbox for waste professionals.

Figure 5. Inspiration box in use.

During a period of nine months many activities took place which generated both many insights about citizens and waste professionals actions, feelings and attitudes about waste and recycling today, and several design concepts including ideas about how the system in various ways could be changed and improved. The activities will only be described in short here in order to give a sense of what took place, and the materials that the research team had to find a suitable deliverable format for (more details in [9]). Several ethnographic inspired field studies were carried out. Some looked into how various professionals within the waste system handled their work, while other field visits focused on various kinds of households, public spaces and shopping centers. A full day inspiration workshop was held including different shop owners, waste collectors, municipalities, researchers and more, where new possible networks were identified and the participants created 'dream projects' about how they would like to change the waste system. A stand was held in a shopping mall to make people passing by reflect on preliminary research findings and extend the field work with their own stories about waste handling. The stories were uploaded on a web blog in order to prolong the transient meeting in the mall. Later three mini-projects were carried out in more detail exploring and experimenting with various as-if scenarios. Various rehearsals of the future illustrating different design concepts were played out through creating and video recording of doll-house

scenarios within workshop setting, and using dolls and making backdrops by using photographs from the field studies, creating and enacting scenarios including prototyping in situ [9].

The deliverable that Vestforbrænding wanted was some kind of a resource material that could be used for a dedicated course on user-driven innovation for project managers in the waste sector, that had not taken part in the pilot project. When searching for a useful format for the deliverable the guiding principle was that we wanted a format that could both include insights and results from the pilot project and resource materials that could be used in new projects. What we liked about the notion of ‘all-in-a-box’ was that it signals that all that is needed is included in the box, and at the same time the box is an open and inclusive format without specific conventions to operate within. In other words it gave some leeway, but also challenges as to what to include and finding formats for the things included.

The three mini projects were documented through one magazine each. With inspiration from the news world this format accommodated many voices and stories in reportages from different project activities but also short descriptions of methods, ideas and design suggestions. Other insights were communicated in brief and direct formats like postcards, flyers or posters, and for instance through seven sharp statements about waste handling, which include recommendations to the waste sector [9]. The most important insights from the field studies were communicated as a combination of images and text named ‘insight cards’. Postcards from all over the world described recycling and waste handling in other countries were included in order to spark reflection and thinking in new directions. The box also included various generative materials that could be used in new projects. For instance various ‘design game’ materials like small wooden dolls, generic game boards, strings, textile materials and miniature versions of the ‘insight cards’, the ‘seven sharp statements about waste’, and the postcards were included in order to assist facilitation of game playing in new projects on recycling and waste handling.

The all-in-the-box deliverable served several purposes. During the training course on user-driven innovation it provided materials for the participants to learn about what this design approach entails. After the course the box was thought of as a mean when communicating with colleagues and persuading managers or politicians to employ new approaches to innovation. And last the box could offer inspiration, tools, approaches and materials for actual planning of new innovation projects.

4. On designing open interpretations

When effort is put into communication of the field data in an open ended and attractive way it creates the needs of having original material that can be transferred into these open ended interpretations. First, it influences on the selection of approach and methods both in gathering and interpreting. Second, whether the resulting tools are poster, booklets or inspiration boxes, they have to be designed. This on one hand highlights the need of design competence in the team, and on the second hand the designing activity as interpretation channel: designers make decisions concerning the content, usability and application. In the following we summarise the design part of the open ended materials.

Designing the layout of the posters required reflection on the content and the message that we wanted to convey through the selected pieces of the data, and on the aesthetic image, i.e. the balance between different graphical

elements. This was a graphic design task combined with storytelling. For instance the reflective activity concerned with questions on what are the quotes that carry an informational meaning, or have an emotional resonance, how many quotes can you fit in a specific size and how many pictures make an interesting combination.

When interpreting the ageing workers' probes data we started to work with mind-maps and visual means of making sense of the data. We also shared stories among ourselves and combined our interpretations. This collaborative reflection became the core of understanding different characters' individual motivations and needs at work. When designing the persona booklets we needed to anonymize the original people the characters represented. This made us illustrate the characters with drawings and combining stories from different individuals. The booklets needed to be in format for easy printing of many copies and sending by mail which set certain guidelines for our creativity.

The Character Game and Senior Expo can be considered as designed objects in them selves. When designing the game the inspiration was gained, among other things, by playing table-top role-playing games, whereas visiting the Contemporary Art Museum provided inspiration while considering means to convey the message through artistic approaches. Also, certain design skills from graphic design to building mock-ups were needed to create game material and the exhibition. Design decisions concerned with how to place the pictures, what quotations to choose and what kind of issues could cause resonance not to mention the aesthetic quality.

Designing the content and packaging of the inspiration box was again a design task combined with research. Choosing functional materials, finalizing the aesthetics of each item required traditional design skills. However, the designers also needed to have insights on design games and other approaches used in the innovation project, also insightful understanding of the content of the material was needed to be able to for instance write and illustrate reportages, edit texts and select the pictures for the cards and other materials.

“Is it representative?” is an often-posed question related to the results of studies presented in this paper. It usually comes from people representing various partners, the companies that are to further design, produce and sell the results from the user-centred design project. Incorporated in the question is a positivistic scientific stand including a belief that user studies/field studies should be representative in order to be interesting (read secure that one is designing the right ‘thing’ for the ‘right people’). An important overall question is what field studies are for, and what their value is in design? What we have seen is that it depends on the project scope, where one is in the project and who are people involved. What we are concerned with here is the learning potentials inherent in the ways we chose to communicate and use results from field studies in design.

An insightful quote found at the Vermeer Center in Delft points to consider the possibilities of communicating open interpretations: *“Seventeenth century art tells stories: about good and evil, about diligence and thoroughness, but also about love and hidden eroticism. Painters are storytellers with images. And so it is with Vermeer: a man of his time who paints contemporary themes. But it is not easy to determine exactly what he wants to tell us. He directs and edits his scenes in such a way that we certainly get some clues, but much still*

remains to keep us guessing.“ Storytelling is used in art, in movies, in literature to convey messages, inspire imagination and reconstruct meanings. Where is the boundary between artistic expression as a tradition to touch, to resonate, to create insights and the user-centred design research? Or do we have to care about those boundaries and instead move more bravely towards the application of more design and artistic expressive ways to enable new interpretations. In creative design, in collaborative innovation processes, information is used not only for its own sake but for the thinking process it initiates.

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